

TRIPLE-SHAPE MEMORY EFFECT OF POLYSTYRENE BASED POLYMER BLENDS

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ABSTRACT

In this study, a triple-shape memory polystyrene based polymer (SMPS) is synthesized, which mainly consists of styrene, vinyl compound, and cross-linking agent (bifunctional monomer). Benzoperoxide is used as the reaction initiator, the polymerization temperature is 75 °C, and the reaction time is 24 h. Differential scanning calorimetry (DSC) and dynamic mechanical analysis (DMA) results demonstrate that the crosslinked styrene based polymer possess two well-separated transition temperatures, which are subsequently used for the fixing/recovery of two

temporary shapes. Furthermore, the versatile triple-shape memory functionality is demonstrated, and the result shows that the material has an excellent triple-shape memory effect. Based on the unique advantages, the SMPS material can be potentially used in sensors and actuators.

1 INTRODUCTION

Shape memory polymers (SMPs) are an exciting kind of stimuli-responsive materials that can deform and recover their original shape by external stimulus.[1-3] Recently, triple shape memory polymers (TSMPs) have attracted more and more attention.[4] In contrast to the classical shape memory polymers which have only one temporary shape and thus exhibit dual-shape effect, TSMPs could remember two temporary shapes and recover sequentially from one temporary shape to the other, and eventually to the permanent shape upon heating. To accomplish this, a TSMP needs to have two separate shape-fixing mechanisms distinguished by separated thermal transitions in the application temperature range.[5-7] This naturally leads to a cascade of three elastic modulus plateaus of decreasing magnitude with increasing temperature. The discovery of the TSMPs is significant, as it provides an additional dimension to the technical potential of SMPs, which have shown great promise in many applications.

In this study, a triple-shape memory polystyrene based polymer (SMPS) is synthesized. Differential scanning calorimetry (DSC) and dynamic mechanical analysis (DMA) results demonstrate that the crosslinked styrene based polymer possess two well-separated transition temperatures, which are subsequently used for

the fixing/recovery of two temporary shapes.

2 EXPERIMENTS

2.1 Materials

Shape memory styrene based polymer was synthesized by using Sigma-Aldrich (St. Louis, MO, USA) chemicals which mainly consisting of styrene, vinyl compound, polystyrene, and cross-linking agent (bifunctional monomer). Benzoperoxide was used as the reaction initiator. All other chemicals and solvents were of reagent grade or better and used without further purification.

2.2 Preparation of shape memory polystyrene

Firstly, pre-weighed a certain amount of neat SMPS, then polymerized between two glass plates with Teflon linings, separated by a 2-mm spacer. The polymerization temperature was 75 °C, and the reaction time was 24 h. After polymerization, the samples were obtained for follow-up characterization and shape memory evaluation.

2.3 Characterization

Thermal properties of the polymers were determined by differential scanning calorimetry (DSC, Q100, TA Instruments, America), and the heating- and cooling-rate of 20 °C min⁻¹ were used.

The dynamic mechanical analysis (DMA) data were obtained by using a DMA (SDTA861, Mettler-Toledo AG Analytical, Switzerland) with tensile resonant mode at a heating rate of 5 °C min⁻¹ from 20 to 160 °C and at a frequency of 1 Hz.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 DSC and DMA Analysis

The differential scanning calorimetry (DSC) and dynamic mechanical analysis (DMA) were used to determine the glass transition temperatures (T_g) of the SMPS. The sample showed two separate glass transitions in both DSC and DMA curves (**Figure 1a, b**). We observed that the first and second T_g is about 50 °C and 110 °C, respectively. A two-step significant modulus decrease was observed in **Figure 1b**. Hence, it was expected that the two-step modulus decrease could result in the release of deformed strain in two steps, so the sample could show two-step strain recovery behavior.[8]

Figure 1: (a) DSC thermogram of SMPS sample; (b) Storage modulus E' of SMPS sample measured by DMA.

3.2 Dual-shape memory properties

Figure 2 shows the macroscopic dual-shape memory recovery process of the SMPS. The size of the stripe-shaped sample is 60 mm × 5 mm × 2 mm (length ×

width × thickness). Firstly, the sample was heated at 130 °C for 5 minutes, and then deformed to temporary spiral shape, cooled to room temperature, released the stress and fixed the temporary shape at last. When reheated the sample to 130 °C, the temporary spiral shape could recover its original shape.

Figure 2: Qualitative process of dual-shape memory fixing and recover.

3.3 Triple-shape memory properties

The SMPS has two distinct transition temperatures (nearly 50 °C and 110 °C) which could endow them with a good triple shape memory effect.[9] Therefore, the triple-shape memory effect was demonstrated in **Figure 3**. The strip-shaped sample with size of 60 mm × 5 mm × 2 mm (length × width × thickness) was deformed to temporary shape (shape B) at 130 °C and fixed at 75 °C, then the sample was further deformed to spiral shape (shape C) at 75 °C and fixed at room temperature for 1 minute. When the temporary shape C was placed in oven at 75 °C for 6 s, it could recover to the shape B, and the temporary shape B could recover to the original shape A in oven (130 °C, reheated) for 20 s.

Figure 3: Qualitative process of triple shape memory fixing and recover.

4 CONCLUSIONS

In summary, we obtained a new polystyrene-based triple shape memory system, which showed an excellent triple-shape memory effect. The DSC and DMA results demonstrated that the SMPS had two transition temperatures, 50 °C and 110 °C, respectively. This SMPS material with excellent triple-shape memory effect could be potentially used in sensors and actuators.

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